

Geneses, Causes, and Ramification of Militancy in FATA in the Post 9/11 Scenario

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Militancy, FATA, Military operations, Maliks, Pkahtunwali, Terrorism

Abstract

The basic aim of the paper is to highlight the impacts of militancy on the Federally Administrated Tribal Area. Strategically the area is very important, and it is situated between Afghanistan and Pakistan. The area also played a very important role in the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan. Before and after 9/11 most of the militants fled to the Tribal areas of Pakistan to seek shelter. The area was used as a launching pad by militants. There were safe sanctuaries of those militants and thus it was a threat to the integrity and sovereignty of Pakistan. As a result, a number of military operations were launched to eliminate those safe sanctuaries. The whole scenario has had some impacts on the life of tribesmen. The paper is an attempt to investigate the root causes of militancy and its impacts on FATA after 9/11.

Introduction

From a strategic point of view, the area of the tribal region of Pakistan has a very magnificent position in the world. Afghanistan shares her border area with Pakistan through this belt from the west and merely a distance of 20 km away from the resource-rich Central Asian Republics. It is like a gateway between Central and South Asia. Besides, the region has a glorious history of war with foreign invaders in the past and in the freedom struggle (Afridi, 2014).

When Pakistan came into being, tribal elders decided to join Pakistan in Bannu Tribal Jirga in a meeting with Mohammad Ali Jinnah in 1947. In the beginning, FATA has kept away from regular constitutional framework due to some certain reasons and ruled under a notorious regulation Frontier Crimes Regulations of 1901. Unfortunately, the successive governments of Pakistan have not given full consideration to the tribal region and often used it for her proxies. The matter became even worse in the era of the 1980s, when Afghan refugees resettled in the region. Slowly and gradually, the tribal areas underwent the influence of powerful lawbreakers due to the absence of a regular mechanism of proper law (Javid, 2011). In such circumstances, the region remained backward in all aspects of life. When the Pakistani high ups have realized the severity of uncertainty as well as anarchism of the miscreants in this area and also felt the pressure International community, Pakistan has started military operations in 2004 for reinstating her writ in FATA (Khan, 2011-12).

Topography of FATA

The tribal belt covers northwestern parts of Pakistan's borderline adjacent to Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province. These are also adjacent to Durand Line. The Durand Line is a common boundary between Pakistan and Afghanistan and the border agreement was signed (Baha, 1978) between the King of Afghanistan and Mortimer Durand of British India in 1893.

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FATA comprises an area of 27220 sq kms equal to 3.4% of the Pakistan land area. According to the 2017 census report, the population of FATA is 5001676 (Census Report of Pakistan, 2017). Economically it is a backward area of Pakistan and some 60% of the population is living below the national poverty line. Natural resources are abandoned. It is a semi-arid area. Most people are associated with agriculture, transport, arms manufacturing, and trade. Due to proximity to war-hit Afghanistan, the smuggling is very common across the border (Baha, 1978). The literacy rate is very low as compare to the rest of the cities in Pakistan. The youngsters of this area are become easy free of the extremists' groups due to the low employment opportunities. That is why the young population gets involved in illegal activities (ICG Asia Report No 125, 2006). Similarly, the prevailing legal system in the area was the main and basic hurdle in the development of the area. The political, and economic exploitation and psychological depression are also contributed to illegal activities (Dawn, November 16, 2009).

Constitutional Status of FATA

According to the 1973 constitution of Pakistan, FATA is an integral part of Pakistan according to article 246 comprising on (Kurrum, Khyber, North Waziristan, South Waziristan, Bajaur, Mohmand, and Orakzai Agency) and Six Frontier Regions (FR): FR Peshawar, FR Bannu, FR Tank, FR Lakki, FR Kohat and FR D.I Khan (Altafullah, 2013). According to the 25th constitutional amendment of the 1973 constitution of Pakistan FATA has merged with Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan (The 25th amendment, 2018).

Pakhtuns code of Conduct (*Pakhtunwali*)

'*Pakhtunwali*' and War on Terror' are the correlated terminologies; scrutinizing the juncture between the two up to what extents and limitations, Pakhtunwali has played a role in the current war, and how it has been exploited or demoted by Pakistanis government, extremists, militants, foreign actors for their appropriated interests. The 'Pakhtuns nationalists' prevailing over a vast area, and its strategic position touches the Afghan border. (Elahi, 2015) Furthermore, the Pakhtuns have conventional codes of conducts and residential norms. Along with it, '*Pakhtunwali*' stands upon many features: worship of Allah, loyalty, unselfishness love for friends, hospitality (*melmestia*), *Panah* (refuge) purdah (covering of whole-body dress), Revenge and Avenge (*Bada*). In all the mentioned qualities, hospitality, refuge, and revenge are the relevant ingredients of a Pakhtun code social life. If Pakhtun does not have these figures in himself, then, he has no right to call upon himself as a Pakhtun-according to their customary and traditional norms. The coming from across the border were treated as guests and they were treated under local traditions (Mohmand, 2003).

Refuge (*Panah*)

'*Panah*' is the principle code of '*Pakhtunwali*', through which the host preserves and safeguards their guests or '*Panah-wanter*' even from their hostile and infidels. Giving *Panah* to an 'oppressed' is conceived and pondered as one of the graceful forms. Insulting one's guests is imagined as disgracing of the hosts which they (Pakhtuns) never accept despite it (Room, 2013). The individuals of 'FATA or Tribal Areas' very worship loving people. For the sake of religion, they never recede even prepare for martyrdom in favor of their Allah, Prophet Muhammad (SAW) and Islam. In the previous century, Pakhtuns have been deceived or mislead by 'Clerics' because of their poor education and illiteracy. (Spain 1994) In addition, the Al-Qaeda and Taliban were treated under the umbrella of this principle (*Panah*) who fought the heroic war against Russians in Afghanistan and also fighting against the USA and NATO, they fled away from Afghanistan in the Post-Americans interest war in Afghanistan. Finally, they supported and favored these Mujahideens for their appropriated and vested for religion. In the earlier stages, the Al-Qaida and Mujahideen entrenched their roots in the daily affairs in the Tribal area (Room, 2013).

Jirga system

Jirga is a very significant pillar of the Pakhtun society and is the only judicial system. It plays a very contributive role in finishing disputes among the tribal. That is why; it is considered a 'backbone' in the 'judicial system' of the 'Pakhun' and tribal society. So, this pillar was led by eminent tribal elders (maliks) and other eloquent (Political Agents) from the government aspect (Shaheen, 2014). Slowly and gradually, the Mujahideen constrained the judicial system (Jirga) in their hands and devout and assassinated the prominent Maliks (tribal elders) who were becoming serious threat and hurdle in their way and affairs. In the initial time, Mujahideen got total control of the psyche of the Pakhtuns (Badshah, 2012). After some time, bribery, nepotism, and corruption were started because of the entrance of violent and extremist agents. These barbaric communities and associations rubbished the atmosphere under the banner and slogan of pro and anti-government. These extremists entered 'Waziristan' and totally hijacked their social and private life concluding; the Taliban assassinated and killed their graceful, respectful and honorable tribal elders, Maliks, under prevailing conspiracies (Tipu, 2013).

Causes of Militancy in FATA

According to Dalai Lama, the dawn of the 21st century would bring peace and prosperity to the world. The development in technology, science, and knowledge would obviously be used for the uplift of humanity but the situation and circumstances were reciprocal to reality. The world was faced with the curse of militancy, religious extremism, destructions and massacres in general while the Muslim states in Particular.

The origin of this curse is not the production of the present day but its ancestry can be found in the cold war era. The military regimes were the breeding source of militancy in Pakistan. The former USSR invasion over Afghanistan in 1979 had cultivated the plant of this curse in the region in general while both in Pakistan and Afghanistan in particular. In this meticulous period, the world was hanging between the two giant powerful bulls (USA and USSR). Because of this bipolarity, both the powers were trying to shift the globe into a unipolar world and become the king without the crown of the world affairs. The tug of war started between these two superpowers in the form of proxies. In these proxy wars, Pakistan was being properly used by the US against the Soviet Union. In this stealthy war against USSR, Pakistan was fully sported by the USA through dollars while Saudi Arabia assistance was observed in the shape of jihadists from various Middle Eastern countries. After the dismemberment of the Russian Federation, the various jihadist groups were left free without any measure of check and balance in Pakistan and Afghanistan. In this way, these warlords, *mujahideen*, and clergy became very influential with the passage of time and consequently, the brunt and presence of two organizations Al Qaeda and Taliban have been experienced in the world. These two associations pretense solemn security intimidation to the world community and then a humdrum day, 9/11 bloodshed, occurred in the history of the USA. This 9/11 incident turned the whole world into the war against terror. The United States of America with her NATO allies attacked poor Afghanistan for revenge. The Musharaf administration also forwarded her hands towards the US and became an ally of America in the war against terror in Afghanistan. The sternness and brunt of this attack were no doubt experienced in the tribal areas of Pakistan as was a veteran in Afghanistan. The Pakistani mujahideen in tribal areas disliked this action of Musharaf administration and reorganized in the umbrella of Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) and other militant groups ([See https://nation.com.pk/21-Feb-2017/causes-of-militancy](https://nation.com.pk/21-Feb-2017/causes-of-militancy)).

In response to Soviet Union occupation in 1979, the Afghan refugees fled to neighboring countries. There are more than 3.5million *Muhajirin* (immigrants) took refuge in Pakistan FATA, the then NWFP, and Baluchistan areas. During this period Pakistan supported the Afghan cause for jihad with money and material. Common perception suggest that the three-decades-long Afghan crisis was responsible for a colossal amount of the weapons in tribal society, drugs, the smuggling of goods, a declining law and order situation, domestic political pressure, stress on the economy, unemployment and human trafficking which clearly affected the social fabric of Pakistan and especially Pukhtoon society of FATA. This has paved ways for the

Talibanization of tribal society, as those tribesmen who fought along with brutal Jihad against the Russians, then joined forces with the Taliban in fighting the other warlords during the subsequent civil war and now resisting the NATO forces in Afghanistan by helping Afghan Taliban. (Mehsud, 2012).

The Soviet occupation in Afghanistan followed by civil war and finally the US-led intervention into Afghanistan following the 9/11 attacks in the US has had a significant impact on the FATA. Local people took part in all these conflicts side-by-side with their Afghan brothers (Haider, 2013).

Military operations in FATA

After the failure of the Shakai Peace Treaty with the Pakistani based Taliban, the government decided to commence military-based operations in the tribal region against the miscreants. In response to this action of the Pakistani govt. the militant groups also started attacks on governmental organizations and security forces within and outside FATA (Govt and Tribes move towards Agreements, 2004).

To root out the miscreant elements from various parts of Pakistan, the government has launched several counter-insurgency operations in FATA and PATA (Provincially Administered Tribal Areas). The govt. of Pakistan was engaged against the militants from Operation Enduring Freedom launched (2001–2002) to Operation Raddul Fasad in clearing the region from these miscreants.

Although, these counter-insurgency operations impacted the tribal areas of Pakistan in all walks of life. These military operations have both positive and negative consequences. On one the area was eliminated from terrorist activities and military bases were the need of the time while on the other hand, it brought a huge economic loss for the people (Musharraf, 2006).

Impacts on FATA

The geneses of insurgency in FATA are linked with the Cold War era. Heavy losses have been recorded by Pakistan in terms of civilian casualties, prosperity, and economy (Afridi, 2013). In spite of this, the region's history is endemic with conflict, the influx of external agents. The current conflict (militancy) has affected the Pashtun way of life in the tribal areas with an unprecedented upset. The ongoing war on terror has largely hit those characteristics of *Pakhtun's* traditional and cultural values which is the core aim of *Pakhtun* codes of conduct (*Pakhtunwali*) (Brain, 2010).

With the passage of time, these high levels of terrorist incidents slowly and gradually started shaking the government writ at domestic, regional and international levels. A large number of influential political leaders and *Maliks* (tribal elders) were killed in committed attacks by the insurgent groups. This phenomenon largely disturbed the political environment of the area. These areas are run under FCR (Frontier Crimes Regulation) in which a political agent is vested with an inconsiderable power but in the post 9/11 scenario, this power is mostly shifted in the hands of military commandants. Similarly, *Jirga* is the only judicial system or a mechanism for bringing out of inter-tribal and intra-tribal disputes. After mounting militancy and the assassination of influential tribal elders, the *Jirgas* were decided by the Taliban commanders (Ibrahim, 2016).

The increasing wave of militancy too abridged the effect of political parties in tribal areas. The woman is excluded completely from the political activities in FATA, but it is worth mentioning here, after the eradication of the militant elements by the successful use of military power of the government against the banned TTP in various parts of FATA the political activities again flourished (Khan, 2011).

According to the analysts, Madrassas in Zia's regime has played a relevant role in enhancing the militancy and extremism. These traditional religious institutes were utilized by Pakistanis and US secret agencies; which outputted, later on, the germs of sectarianism in Pakistan. Moreover, these militant groups were abetted by foreign assistance (Yousafzai, 2011).

The reason for the enhancing militancy is due to the lack of justice and the irrational distribution of powers. The unemployment is one of the serious menaces; aiding militancy and extremism. Besides this, unemployed individuals can easily be attracted to the dominion of extremism – by giving or granting them

incentives. On the other hand, "Inequality in the society always creates a lust for power", and the exploited or degraded individuals are used to fund by these militants and extremist groups for attaining self-independence or autonomy. In the last, for obtaining or getting equality, justice, respect, and lustful desires, they used the banner of Islam; which, resultantly, exploited the banner of Islam (Ahmad, 2013).

The terrorist activities have adversely affected the tribal people's social fabrics as well as life. Ever-increasing terrorist attacks in public places e.g. markets, public and government offices and private organizations have decreased the employment opportunities. The people were feeling fear in going to market, shopping malls and even their workplaces. In 2009-10, the unemployment ratio augmented from 0.10 million to 0.12 million as a result of fanatic attacks in metropolitan and settled areas of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The official data is unavailable for FATA but we can easily calculate the unemployment ratio in FATA with the prevailing intensity of militancy in tribal areas. Similarly, the counter-insurgency measures in those areas have also left grave effects on FATA's people's life. Military operations and long curfew hours have also damaged the economic activities, their lives, homes, villages, properties, and even cities and became IDPs in the adjacent settled areas (Khan, 2013).

Internal Migration

Although, with this massive mass migration from war-affected areas to settled districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to D.I Khan, Peshawar as well as Bannu faced with great hurdles in the IDP camps but they quickly restored themselves. The positive outcome of this migration on the life of tribal people was/is observing local culture, the difference in lifestyle and many other social changes. Pardah is given very importance in Pakhtun culture in general while in tribal is particular (Azam, 2014). in tribal areas females were not permitted to visit or depart to Bazars, marketplace or shopping centers and even to hospital without any male family members. In maternity cases, the domestic treatments were provided to women in homes. The tribal women were/are unaware of modern healthcare facilities. The government of Pakistan provided female doctors, LHV's and nurses to these IDP camps for women awareness about child-mother health (Khan, 2011).

Similarly, male members of the family interacted with the local population. They started businesses in these areas. Many families have settled in rural areas and started agriculture in the settled areas; the tribal people are also familiar with the legal system. Many people put their children in schools because they knew the importance of education for a society or nation. Education is the only key and like a backbone in its development and progress for a nation.

Educational Impacts

A large number of educational institutions were blown up by militants, while many were destroyed and dysfunctional during military operations in the warring zones. In this situation, many children were kept away from their schooling. This was a much-deteriorated period for our school-going generation (Malak, 2015).

It is sad and deteriorated fact that in the war-hit areas almost 458 educational institutions were destroyed and closed during militancy and military operations. In the mentioned figure 317 boys' educational institutions dysfunction while 141 female schools were inactive (Naqvi, & Shah, 2012).

Total educational institutions shattered in FATA

S/No.	Agencies	Boys	Girls	Total
1	Bajaur Agency	68	27	95
2	Mohmand Agency	66	22	88
3	Khyber Agency	31	27	58
4	Orakzai Agency	23	16	61

5	Kurram Agency	45	11	34
6	N.W. Agency	23	9	32
7	S. W. Agency	29	6	35
8	Frontier Region Peshawar	11	4	15
9	Frontier Region Kohat	17	15	32
11	Frontier Region Tank	2	2	4
12	Frontier Region Lakki	2	2	4
	Total	317	141	458

Source: FATA Research Centre

Effects of War on Economic Status of the Local People

The war on terror and insurgency has left deteriorating impacts in every walk of life of Pakistani society. It decreased the home-based economic activities in the first step. It also affected the other important economic sectors such as foreign direct investment, business productivity, tax collection and exports to a very worsen decline. The whole Gross Domestic Produces (GDP) increase suffered because of a severe wave of terrorism. The second factor is financial losses and the rise in the credit risk of the country which indicates that Pakistan underwent financial losses by weakening to pay back the loans it acquired from financial organizations particularly the IMF (Economic Survey of Pakistan, 2013). Unemployment is the third indirect cost, which is the massive setback of prevailing unrest in the affected areas like KPK and FATA. High-level losses in the agriculture sector have spoiled the businesses and tourist resorts, reciprocally, thousands of people have lost their jobs. The fourth one is the huge displacement of the local population. Insurgency and counter-insurgency efforts by the Pakistani govt. millions of people were displaced from FATA into settled districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The fifth deteriorating cost of insurgency in the delay of implementation of development projects in KPK & FATA (Pasha, 2013).

War affects distinct arenas and it is a transitional stage from progress to backwardness. The war on terror has greatly influenced the region; it degraded FATA economically and geographically, socially, politically and literally or educationally. It is said, "FATA or Tribal areas are used as business route, because of its juncture and connection, strategically, with Afghanistan most of the containers were used for fetching the goods across the border. But in the status quo, the border has been sealed with elevated fences, which resulted in the blocked of business and trade with Afghanistan through its geographical location. Furthermore, the social impacts of militancy are also essential ingredients to be discussed (Khan, 2013).

The people of FATA in their norms have been affected. After starting the war in FATA, they were dislodged from their houses, three hundred Maliks were killed by the extremists and violent communities. Along with this, they were mentally as well as physically tortured. Furthermore, they were deprived of their businesses, the poverty rate was enhanced which is the leaning or persuading factor towards militancy. In the last, after implementing 'curfew' by the 'Pakistanis security forces most of the patients died due to inaccessible in time treatment. The Political scenario of FATA was very alarming from extremism. In various tribal areas like; Mohmand Agency, Waziristan and Bajaur they were attacked, which fainted the governmental and political arena of administration, moreover, the political parties were not allowed for interrupting the political domain of the country. In addition to it, the relevant or the important square of education is also discouraged.

Foreign Direct Investment

Terrorism directly impacts foreign direct investment (FDI). The increase in the intensity of terrorism drops down the ratio of FDI which leads to a decrease in Gross domestic products of the country. The investors prefer always safe and secure region for their investment that is why servable and peaceful countries always receive high foreign investment as compared to unsecured areas. Unfortunately, Pakistan is failed in

receiving the attention of foreign investors because of the insecure and unfavorable condition of FATA and KPK (Ali, 2013).

Agriculture Sector

Pakistan is an agro-based economy it means that the agriculture sector plays a very significant role in boosting up of its GDP growth. For the last ten or more than ten years, the agriculture sector of Pakistan is being observed in decline due to various reasons, but terrorism and counter military operations in FATA are the main causes of deterioration of this sector. The agriculture sector is the source of employment in Pakistan. Agriculture and farming is the primary source of livelihood for almost 80% of the population in these areas. Due to militancy and counter militancy operations in FATA, about (60-70) % of the total fruit produces have been destroyed completely. Militants have blown up the bridges in bomb blasts, artillery shelling, translocation of the local population to safe and secure places and the imposition of frequent curfews by security forces consequently, the formers landowners and dealers had to face losses in billions (Rashid, 2014).

Agriculture Growth Rate Percentage in Pakistan 2004-2011

Year	Agriculture Growth (%)	Major Crops	Minor Crops	Livestock	Fishery	Forestry
2004-05	6.5	17.7	1.5	2.3	0.6	-32.4
2005-06	6.3	-3.9	0.4	15.8	20.8	-1.1
2006-07	4.1	7.7	-1.0	2.8	15.4	-5.1
2007-08	1.0	-6.4	10.9	4.2	9.2	-13.0
2008-09	4.0	7.8	-1.2	3.1	2.3	-3.0
2009-10	0.6	-2.4	-7.8	4.3	1.4	2.2
2010-11	1.2	-4.0	4.8	3.7	1.9	-0.4

Source: Economic Survey of Pakistan

Tourism Sector

Pakistan is gifted with the highest mountain ranges, rivers and various famous natural and beautiful resorts of the world. There are many historical, natural and adorable places of travel. Several picnic spots are situated in the war-affected areas. Due to the curse of terrorism, the tourists were feeding fear in visiting these areas the foreign tourists are still not prepared to agree to visit Pakistan. So, the prevailing terrorism and extremism completely destructed the local tourist industry this situation has a negative impact on Pakistan's economy (Michael, 2007). Pakistani society is badly affected by the ever-increasing activities of the militant groups when they extended their terrorist attacks from tribal areas to settle. After the bomb blast in Marriot hotel Islamabad in 2007-08, the numbers of tourists have abundant to visit Pakistani tourist sites and historical places in these areas. This situation adversely affected regions. The tourists like to visit those places which are and secure. The double trouble situation also led to a decline in hotel events like marriages and conventions etc. The tourism sector has also left a deteriorated effect on the economic condition of the country in general while war-affected areas in particular. It drops down the occupancy rates from 60% to 40% in the last decade (PIPS, 2010).

Tribal Areas in the post Counter Insurgency Measures: mainstreaming FATA

No nation can reach the height of glory unless they are educated, this sphere of FATA mostly swayed away by the terrorist groups. After starting or inaugurating rescue-operations against the violent groups, educational institutions like schools and colleges were banned from both the military and the Taliban. Co-education was outlawed by the Mujahideen and Taliban in the Tribal Areas. Along with it, it also struck out

the KPK and its citizens. The tribal women did not participate in any political activity before militancy and military operations but in 2013 general elections a woman namely 'Badam Zari' admitted her documents as an independent candidate from Bajaur Agency. Besides, different women organizations like 'Takra Qabaili Khwaindy' and FSO 'FATA student's organization women wing' are playing a very active role in women's rights in FATA. In the recent political activities and reforms package for FATA, the women social activists from the tribal region have demanded complete participation from the pout. These women organizations have also demanded equal representation in the legislation process in FATA reforms and expressed their desire for the FATA merger in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (Ibrahim, 2016).

This is a great development in FATA's social life that has not been observed before military operations. The women were not allowed to approach Bazars and shopping malls or even hospitals without male family members. Female higher education was not considered good in the tribal society and women were under house arrest but the situation is totally different nowadays. Women may now approach public places, restaurants, and even the government or private institutions freely.

Emblazonry of weapons is considered as a male dress in the tribal society but now they put down their weapons and diverted their attention towards education and other constructive thinking for uplifting their tribal society (Haider, 2016).

Although it was disastrous in the form of economic, political and social destruction, the Pakistani govt. and military establishment has always utilized its tribal regions for their proxies in the past and still further. But the war against terror exposed the international community and its strategic importance. Before militancy and military operations and the aftermath of the 9/11 incident, this area was not under consideration of the govt. of Pakistan, policymakers and in the eyes of international players. Due to the increasing intensity of militancy in the region attracted the attention of Pakistan's policymakers for political reforms, otherwise, the area will remain as such it was before (Khan, 2016).

Border Management Mechanism:

Similarly, another positive achievement is the mechanism of border management. To stop militant's infiltration across the border and also to put an end to consistent blames and accusations of Kabul over Islamabad for supporting the Taliban attacks in Afghanistan. For this purpose, the government of Pakistan is installing fencing on the Pak-Afghan borders. This border management mechanism includes the constructions of various military posts, entrance gates, aerial surveillance as well as valid travel documents. (Shah, 2015)

Defense Expenditures and Rehabilitation Process:

Before 9/11, the tribal belt of Pakistan is considered very peaceful and secure. After the emergence of miscreant elements in FATA the govt. under compulsion decided to deploy its armed forces in tribal areas. To eradicate militant's hides out and eliminate the safe heavens of the terrorist groups, the security forces started militancy operations against them with the launching of such operations, the defense expenditure must be raised (Irshad, 2011). For security, civil relief operation and rehabilitation of IDP's Pakistan had to spend \$ 123.13 billion almost Rs 10.373 trillion Pakistani in direct and indirect cost in the last 16 years (Bari, 2013).

Conclusion

Terrorism and extremism have not only affected the foundation of federally Administered Tribal Areas but also uprooted the social fabric of the tribal region of Pakistan. The growing militancy is still paying a grave cost in the shape of fragile economic growth, human losses as well as the destruction of infrastructure. This curse has also shattered the soft image of Pakistan in the international community. The major impacts of terrorism on tribal society are changing their outlooks, their social behaviors, their strict cultural norms and their way of life in all respects.

No doubt, the people of FATA are faced with a very crucial environment as compared to the rest of Pakistani. They saw the destruction of their land, property, and their businesses in the hands of militants as well as in the hands of security forces. These people are also the eye-witnessed of their dears whiling slaughtering by the militant. They have been expelled from their villages in the name counter-insurgency measures.

The war on terror has both positive and negative impacts on the lives of tribal people. FATA is the only region, which is out of the sphere of the regular legal and constitutional framework of Pakistan. Keeping in view the gravity of the situation, the government of Pakistan decided on the mainstreaming of FATA. The government has given full attention to the development of the area. In 2018, under the 25th constitution amendment, FATA has merged with Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan.

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